

IMPROVEMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS OF REGIONAL TOURISM DEVELOPMENT (IN THE CASE OF KASHKADARYA REGION)

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Abstract. *In this scientific-practical article, the issue of improving the organizational and economic mechanisms of regional tourism development is studied in the case of Kashkadarya region. The author developed proposals and recommendations for the development of tourism in the region.*

Keywords: *regional tourism, tourism infrastructure, Kashkadarya region, barrier-free tourism, tourism.*

Introduction

In the modern world, tourism is considered as a socio-economic phenomenon that directly and indirectly affects the development of all related infrastructure. In the 21st century, tourism is based on the high level of development of transport, social and service sectors, which ultimately turns it into a highly profitable sector of the economy.

According to the World Tourism Organization, today tourism is one of the most profitable and dynamic sectors of the world economy. In terms of profitability, it ranks second after oil extraction and processing. Tourism accounts for nearly 6 percent of the world's gross national product, 7 percent of global investment, one in 16 jobs, 11 percent of global consumer spending, and 5 percent of all tax revenues. In this regard, the tourism industry is actively developing with the support of the government in many countries [1].

Within the framework of the 3 directions of the "Strategy of Actions" for the strategic development of the country in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, the mission and goal is to "rapidly develop the tourism industry, increase its role and share in the economy, diversify and improve the quality of tourist services, and expand the tourism infrastructure." was promoted, and as a result of the measures implemented within this framework, the tourism infrastructure was improved. In particular, the number of wi-fi zones reached 230, the number of information centers serving tourists reached 33, the number of hotels and hostels reached 914, and the number of buses serving tourists reached 133 [2]. In the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, comprehensive development of regions, bringing their infrastructure to the level of world standards, development of barrier-free tourism infrastructure, development of infrastructure of tourism and cultural heritage objects, and improvement of effective use of more than 8 thousand cultural heritage objects are addressed [12].

But this is not enough. First of all, in terms of promotion of tourist products and quality service, we are seriously lagging behind the international level in terms of the condition of tourist facilities and vehicles. In addition, the funds allocated by the state for the development of tourism are not high, they amount to 3.4% of the GDP. However, this indicator is 21.9% in Thailand, 16.1% in Tunisia, 13.2% in Azerbaijan from the CIS countries, and 7.8% in Tajikistan [3].

Public investment in infrastructure and sometimes expensive tourism infrastructure encourages investment by many small businesses. Over time, the initial investment in tourism attracts more investment in the supporting sectors of the economy: hotels, restaurants, shopping centers, ports, airports, etc.

In the world experience, it is possible to see that the main tool for the development of tourism in the regions is the state, which stimulates the development of various directions of tourism in the regions and thereby creates organizational conditions for increasing the level of employment, increasing the gross income of the region, and developing infrastructure. .

There are regions in our country where tourism needs to be developed with state support. One such region is Kashkadarya region. According to the data of September 2022, the services provided for foreign tourists are very low in Kashkadarya, and no tourism services are provided in Shahrisabz, Yakkabog, Qamashi, Kasbi districts [4]. For this reason, extensive research on the topic is urgent.

Literature review

In the research of the world economy, theoretical and methodological issues have been considered based on various aspects of the development of the tourism market in the literature prepared by world scientists. Among the scientists of the CIS countries M.B.Birzhaakov, V.S.Bogolyubov, V.I.Azar, I.T.Balabanov, A.Yu.Aleksandrova, M.N.Dmitriev, A.B.Zdorov, N.B.Zorin, V.A.Kvartalganov[5] theoretical analysis of economic relations characteristic of tourism economy, tourism market economy topics such as basics and practical issues, as well as problems of using tourist resources, are studied in scientific works. I.S. Tukhliev, B.Kh.Toraev, D.Q.Usmanova, N.Tukhliev, K.Kh.Abdurakhmonov, Ye.V.Golisheva, N.S.Ibragimov, M.Q.Pardaev, A.F.Saidov, A.Abduvakhidov, M.T.Alieva on the priority issues of tourism development in our national economy and their solutions , B.SH.Safarov, T.Tashmuratov, O.Khamidov [6] and a number of other economist-scientists scientific researches were used and studied.

Most tourism researchers view tourism as a modern phenomenon that arises from the need to enjoy the joys of life, the nature of various attractive landscapes, the growing sense of joy, the sense of pleasure and living, as well as the sense of enjoyment of life[7].

On the other hand, tourism was recognized by the International Academy of Tourism in 1961 as an expression called recreat, which is defined as a human activity that works to achieve this type of travel, an industry that helps to satisfy the desires of the tourist [8].

Therefore, tourism is another aspect of activities and events that take place within or outside the borders of any country, and therefore it has become a social, cultural and mass media that is reflected in all the entertainment and activities of that country.

Analysis and results

Cities in our country with ancient rich tourism potential, such as Bukhara, Tashkent, Samarkand, have always been the center of attention of foreign and local tourists. They have attracted tourists with their historical monuments, architecture and culture.

The initiative of the government to create tourist areas is widely implemented even in the regions that do not have many historical monuments, but have their own nature and national cuisine. Kashkadarya region is one of the regions with a rich cultural heritage, national values and traditions, attracting foreign tourists with its unique nature. Today, 1,311 objects of cultural heritage are registered in the region, of which 1,41 are archaeological, 200 are architectural, 43 are

statues, and 27 are attractions. Along with the protection of these cultural heritage objects, it is very important to carry out reconstruction and repair work in them. There are many examples of our national heritage, especially in Kitab, Shahrisabz, Yakkabog, Guzor and Karshi districts. 45 hotels operate in the region. The most interesting thing is that their prices are much lower compared to other regions of the country (Table 1).

The government approved the plan of measures for the establishment of new tourism destinations in Kashkadarya region.

According to it, the following will be organized in the region:

ethnotourism direction - 5 guest houses will be built in the villages of Gilan and Kol. Ethnovillage - a military training camp of Amir Temur's fighters will also be founded;

agrotourism direction - in the villages of Varganza and Hazrat Bashir. The "Pomegranate" festival will be held within this direction;

extreme tourism - in Tatar, Zarmast and Vari villages. 5 guest houses, 5 campsites and 10 huts will be built in each of them;

ecological tourism - in the villages of Sarchashma and Suvtushar;

astronomical tourism - in the territory of the Kitab latitude station.

A MICE-tourism direction will be opened under the "City of Festivals" brand [9].

In addition, the Cabinet of Ministers approved the procedure for the use of benefits and subsidies, as well as the amount of the local tourist tax charged for accommodation, as determined by the Decree of the President of February 9, 2021. According to it:

— "Fergana-Urganch-Fargana", "Termiz-Urganch-Termiz" and "Karshi-Urganch-Karshi" flights;

— "Termiz-Karshi-Khiva", "Khiva-Urganch-Nukus" and "Termiz-Karshi-Samarkand" railway routes were launched [10].

In order to provide the opportunity to travel through the territories of Uzbekistan to tourists with any social opportunities, "barrier-free tourism" has developed, and since 2023, the implementation of the "Barrier-free tourism infrastructure development program" has been determined in the republic's territories in the following stages. placed:

- in 2023 — Samarkand, Bukhara, Khorezm and Kashkadarya regions;
- in 2024 — Fergana, Namangan, Andijan and Jizzakh regions;
- In 2025 — Republic of Karakalpakstan, Navoi, Surkhandarya and Syrdarya regions;
- in 2026 — Tashkent city and Tashkent region;
- Financing of the "Barrier-free tourism infrastructure development program" is carried out through the state budget of the Republic, sponsorship funds and grants;
- The above goals will be included in the five-year New Uzbekistan development strategy and the state program for its implementation [11].

Table 1.

Hotels in the regions and their starting prices

	Regions	Number of hotels	Prices
	Bukhara region	193	It starts from 120 thousand soums
	Samarkand region	149	It starts from 110 thousand soums
	Tashkent region	109	It starts from 185 thousand soums

	Fergana region	98	It starts from 240 thousand soums
	Khorezm region	82	It starts from 70 thousand soums
	Republic of Karakalpakstan	60	It starts from 100 thousand soums
	Kashkadarya region	45	It starts from 80 thousand soums
	Jizzakh region	43	It starts from 60 thousand soums
	Namangan region	36	It starts from 100 thousand soums
	Navoi region	34	It starts from 200 thousand soums
	Surkhandarya region	29	It starts from 60 thousand soums
	Andijan region	21	It starts from 60 thousand soums
	Syrdarya region	14	It starts from 60 thousand soums

Along with the implemented measures, there are problems in the area that are waiting to be solved. Including:

- The need to build a new world-standard terminal of the international airport;
- Inadequate internal roads leading to historical monuments and beautiful nature of the region;
- Lack of tourism personnel in the province;
- Absence of guest houses, inns or hotels in the regions where the nature of the region is beautiful and there is a possibility to develop gastronomic tourism, and even if there are, there are no conditions for providing services to foreign guests;
- The lack of demand for restaurants and services that can show the gastronomic possibilities of the region;
- The main thing is that the touristic image of the region has not been formed.

Conclusion and recommendations

As a result of the conducted analysis, the following recommendations were formed:

- Providing incentives to business entities providing tourist services in the region;
- To open specializations that train personnel in tourism, restaurant services, cooking in regional higher and secondary special educational institutions;
- The ecological potential of the region creates conditions for the development of ecological tourism there. In particular, it is advisable to organize entertainment and fun activities such as horse riding, trekking, camel travel, rafting in the area.
- Improvement of transport infrastructure in the region, etc.

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